

Comparative analysis of Grammatical Numbers System in Russian and Sanskrit

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Abstract

This study provides a detailed comparison of the Grammatical Number systems in Russian and Sanskrit, two highly inflected languages from distinct language families. The research is aimed at the morphological, syntactic, and semantic characteristics of numbers in both languages, comparing them. This study investigates how Numbers are conveyed syntactically in both languages by examining relevant linguistic literature and analysing noun phrases, agreement patterns, and syntactic structures linked to Numbers. The research discusses semantic distinctions, quantification, and conceptualizations connected with singular and plural entities, as well as how Numbers contribute to the semantic interpretation and meaning of nouns in both languages. This study shed highlights on the distinctive features of number agreement and its significance for linguistic typology.

Keywords: Russian, Sanskrit, Number, Agreement, Morphology, Inflection, Markers, Syntax, Semantics, Language Typology

1. Introduction

Language is a key tool for personal communication, with surprising variation around the world. The grammatical number system, which allows speakers to communicate numbers, countable things, and the concept of plurality, is one feature of language that greatly adds to its complexity. Russian and Sanskrit stand out as different entities with remarkable histories and linguistic patterns within the diverse fabric of languages.

This research article compares and contrasts the grammatical number systems of Russian and Sanskrit. It aims to elucidate upon their unique characteristics, syntactic patterns, and semantic intricacies linked to conveying number distinctions by an in-depth analysis of these two languages. It investigates the similarities and contrasts between these two languages.

Russian, an Indo-European language (Beekes, R. S. P. 2011; Clackson, J. 2007; Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D 2009; Mallory, J. P., & Adams, D. Q. 2006), has a complex grammatical number system with sophisticated declension patterns and morphological markers for singular, plural, and even dual forms. Sanskrit, an ancient Indo-Aryan language, has a complicated grammatical number system with numerous inflections and declensions.

The number is a linguistic category that carries semantic implications. The study also focuses on the semantic aspects of expressing Numbers in Russian and Sanskrit, two languages known for their rich inflectional systems (The syntax of number. 2000). By examining their semantic distinctions, quantification strategies, and conceptualizations, the study aims to investigate how

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Numbers shape the semantic interpretation of nouns in these languages and aims to find out linguistic typological difference between both languages. This article will help Indian as well as Russian students and researchers. Indian students, who know Sanskrit language, learns Russian language can carry out comparative study and learning as well as Russian students who are learning Sanskrit language, this could be helpful for them.

A comparative linguistic method is used in this work, which draws on extensive historical texts, and grammatical studies. It aims to present an analysis of the structures of the grammatical number systems in Russian and Sanskrit by investigating the morphological, syntactic, and semantic elements of their structures.

Furthermore, this study investigates the underlying cognitive processes and conceptualizations linked with number expression in different languages. It contributes to our knowledge of the cognitive factors that create language and human thought by investigating how speakers of Russian and Sanskrit see and categorise objects based on their grammatical number.

Finally, this comparative study not only adds to our understanding of Russian and Sanskrit, but it also highlights on the typological diversity and evolution of grammatical number systems across languages. We gain a better understanding of the rich tapestry of human language and its underlying cognitive foundations by unravelling the complexities of these systems.

2. *Grammatical number system*

The grammatical number system is a linguistic characteristic that uses quantity to categorise and distinguish nouns and pronouns other parts of speech. Let's look at how the grammatical number system works in Sanskrit and Russian, two languages with interesting features in this regard.

The ancient Indo-Aryan language Sanskrit includes a comprehensive grammatical number system (Bhandarkar, S. R. G.1870). It differentiates between three types of numbers: singular, dual, and plural. When referring to two distinct entities, the dual form is employed. Nouns, describing words, pronouns, and verbs in Sanskrit are all inflected to represent the varied numbers. Beyond the fundamental singular-plural distinction found in many languages, the process allows exact and explicit transmission of numbers. In contrast, Russian has a more sophisticated grammatical number system than many Indo-European languages (Baldi, P. 1983; Beekes, R. S. P. 2011; Clackson, J. 2007; Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D. 2009; Mallory, J. P., & Adams, D. Q. 2006). Like English, it distinguishes between single and plural, but it also has a unique feature known as the "dual number." When there are exactly two entities involved, the dual is utilised. However, the dual form is only used in specific contexts, such as when referring to pairs of body parts or objects that naturally come in pairs. Most Russian nouns and pronouns inflect primarily for singular and plural.

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The grammatical number system influences not just nouns and pronouns, but also other parts of speech such as adjectives and verbs in both Sanskrit and Russian. The agreement of these elements is required to ensure grammatical consistency. Adjectives and verbs must be inflected in order to correspond to the number of the noun or pronoun they modify or agree with. While Sanskrit has a more extensive grammatical number system than Russian, both languages emphasise the importance of number as a grammatical category. This emphasises the importance of quantity in communication and the need to express precise information about the number of objects, people, or concepts under discussion.

The grammatical number system is very important in Sanskrit and Russian. Sanskrit uses a system of singular, dual, and plural numbers to provide accurate quantity distinctions, whereas Russian differentiates between singular, plural, and a limited dual number. Understanding the grammatical number system is critical for building grammatically acceptable sentences and accurately conveying quantity in various languages.

3. *Morphological Aspects*

Number is a significant linguistic category in a language that distinguishes between single, dual, and plural elements. It enables speakers to convey the quantity or number associated with nouns, pronouns, and other of speech. The huge language family Proto-Indo-European (PIE) features a dual number in addition to singular and plural forms (Beekes, R. S. P. 2011; Clackson, J. 2007; Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D 2009; Mallory, J. P., & Adams, D. Q. 2006). This feature was preserved in many descendant languages, including Ancient Greek and Sanskrit, which both have complex inflectional systems for expressing numbers.

Among other languages, Sanskrit and Russian have morphological features that allow for the expression of numbers. The study of the internal structure and shape of words is referred to as morphology. Morphology in the context of numbers refers to the unique affixes, endings, or alterations made to words to represent different numerical values (Booij, G. 2007; Haspelmath, M.1996, 2007). Sanskrit and Russian have complex inflectional systems that enable for sophisticated numerical expression (Bright & Deshpande, 1995; Gribble & Comrie, 1982; Kreindler & Comrie, 1982).

Sanskrit, an ancient Indo-Aryan language, has a complex inflectional system. To signify the singular, dual, and plural numbers, it utilises several case systems, each with its own distinct ending. The dual number, which was acquired from Proto-Indo-European, remains in Sanskrit but has grown less productive over time. It is mostly used in specific settings, such as when referring to body parts or suggesting natural pairs. Nouns, adjectives, and pronouns in Sanskrit have different forms for each number, and their inflectional endings change correspondingly. In Sanskrit, the morphology of numbers provides a vast array of patterns and rules guiding the creation of dual and plural forms. Bright and Deshpande (1995)

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Russian, a Slavic language, has a rich inflectional system as well as a developed morphology for expressing numbers (Booij, G. 2007; Haspelmath, M.1996, 2007). In Russian, nouns have singular, dual, and plural forms. In Russian, the dual number signifies two entities, but the plural number denotes more than two. Russian nouns have their endings changed to reflect the right number. Adjectives, pronouns, and verb forms all have number distinctions and go through inflectional changes accordingly (Gribble & Comrie. 1982; Kreindler & Comrie. 1982). When morphological numbers in Sanskrit and Russian are compared, various distinct traits and patterns emerge. While both languages keep the dual number, their usage and effectiveness differ. Sanskrit retains a wider dual system, but Russian uses it only in specific instances. Furthermore, the creation of plural forms in Sanskrit and Russian follows separate patterns, indicating differences in their respective language families (Bright & Deshpande. 1995; Gribble & Comrie. 1982; Kreindler & Comrie. 1982). The study of morphological numbers in Sanskrit and Russian reveals important information on the evolution and diversity of language systems. The distinctive characteristics and patterns discovered in each language help us comprehend the grammatical structures and cultural circumstances in which these languages evolved" (Bright & Deshpande. 1995; Gribble & Comrie. 1982; Kreindler & Comrie. 1982; Comrie. 1981; Deshpande. 2007).

Numbers are morphologically marked in Russian nouns, adjectives, pronouns, and verbs. Nouns have unique singular and plural forms that often require changes in endings (Corbett, 2000). In the plural form, the noun "стол" (table) becomes "столы" (tables). Adjectives, like nouns, go through similar inflectional changes to match the number of the noun they modify (Dunn, J. A., & Khairov, S.. 2013; Kemple, B.. 2012; Wade, T. 2020; Corbett. 2000). Russian pronouns have a more comprehensive set, with separate forms for singular, plural, and even a dual number category (Forsyth, 1970).

In Russian, verbs agree with subjects (Bailyn, J. F., & Bailyn, J. F. 2012). Sanskrit, too, has a complex morphological system for representing numbers. In Sanskrit, nouns, adjectives, and pronouns have singular and plural forms (Whitney. 2003). Sanskrit pronouns, like Russian pronouns, include a dual number category (Pini, 6th century BCE). Sanskrit verbs agree with subjects by using appropriate suffixes for singular and plural agreement (Macdonell, A. A. 2014; Whitney, W. D. 1896; Joshi, S. D. 1979.; Macdonell 1914). For example, the verb "गच्छति" (gacchati), meaning "he/she/it goes," singular changes to "गच्छन्ति" (gacchanti), meaning "they go," in the plural form.

Inflectional methods for expressing Numbers in Russian entail changes in Noun and describing word endings "like adjective, possessive pronoun, demonstrative pronoun, participle." The specific changes are determined by the noun or adjective's declension pattern (Corbett, 2000). Nouns can be classified into one of six declensions, each having its own set of singular and plural inflectional endings. Adjectives and nouns agree in gender, case, and number, resulting in a variety of inflectional patterns (Corbett, 2000). Verbs have different ends for singular and

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plural forms. To convey numbers in Sanskrit, inflectional processes including changes in endings are used. In Sanskrit, nouns are classified into declensions, and the inflectional endings differ depending on the declension class (Whitney, 2003). In Sanskrit, adjectives agree with nouns in gender, case, and number.

4. *Morphological Markers*

In Russian, numbers are expressed primarily through modifications in noun and adjective endings, which serve as morphological markers. These inflectional endings aid in identifying between singular and plural things (Corbett, 2000). The endings of nouns change to represent the appropriate number. Adjectives that agree with nouns in number and case have unique singular and plural forms (Corbett, 2000). Russian's inflectional system allows for the presentation of singular, plural, and dual number categories (Bailyn, 2012; Forsyth, 1970).

In Sanskrit, particular morphological markers are used to represent numbers. In Sanskrit, nouns and adjectives have separate forms for singular and plural, with different inflectional endings. The endings vary depending on the case, gender, and number of the noun or adjective (Whitney, 2003). Sanskrit pronouns have separate forms for singular, plural, and dual numbers, creating additional distinction for numerical values (Pini, 6th century BCE).

In addition to nouns, adjectives, and pronouns, verbs are used to convey numbers in Sanskrit. The agreement marks in verbs change depending on the number of the subject and object. The inflectional endings of the verb root, known as conjugation, differ depending on the verb's person, number, tense, and mood (Macdonell, 1914). This system enables Sanskrit to signify agreement in verbal phrases with the number of the subject and object.

Russian and Sanskrit morphological markers and inflectional systems provide distinct perspectives into the expression of numbers in each language. While Russian generally uses noun and adjective endings to differentiate between numbers, Sanskrit extends the difference to nouns and pronouns and verb agreement markers. These linguistic traits add to the depth and complexity of Russian and Sanskrit morphological systems, providing essential information on these languages' grammatical structures and cultural contexts.

5. *Syntactic Aspects*

Number is a linguistic category that is important in syntactic structures. By comparing and contrasting their syntactic approaches, it is possible to identify the distinctive features and patterns in each language, as well as cross-linguistic variation and the influence of language families on syntactic expression. Russian has usually subject-verb agreement, which means that the verb inflects to match the number or pronoun of the subject. The existence of plural subjects causes the verb to use plural agreement markers (Corbett, 2000).

Russian follows a proximity principle in coordinated noun phrases, where the verb agrees with the nearest noun according to which verb gains the verbal form in terms of number (Bailyn, J.

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F., & Bailyn, J. F. 2012). Sanskrit, like Russian, has subject-verb agreement. The verb agrees with the subject's number, gaining single or plural agreement markers (Whitney. 2003). Sanskrit, on the other hand, develops a system of agreement known as "pada," in which verbs agree with the number of the noun in certain constructions (Pini, 6th century BCE).

Noun phrases in Russian are often designated for Number using agreement patterns. Adjectives, pronouns, and possessives must all agree with the noun they modify in terms of number (Corbett, 2000). For example, in the noun phrase "старые столы" (old tables), both the adjective "старые" (old) and the noun "столы" (tables) show plural agreement. Russian also employs quantifiers, such as "несколько" (several) and "много" (many), to express approximate or indefinite quantities (Dunn, J. A., & Khairov, S. 2013; Kemple, B. 2012; Wade, T. 2020; Forsyth. 1970).

Numbers are expressed in Sanskrit using similar grammatical approaches. Number is expressed in noun phrases using agreement patterns. Adjectives, pronouns, and determiners must all agree with the noun they modify in terms of number (Whitney. 2003). For example, in the noun phrase "पुस्तकाः विचित्राः" (interesting books), both the adjective "विचित्राः" (interesting) and the noun "पुस्तकाः" (books) show plural agreement. Sanskrit also utilizes quantifiers, such as "अनेकः" (many) and "अल्पः" (few), to express approximate or indefinite quantities (Macdonell, A. A. 2014; Whitney, W. D. 1896; Joshi, S. D. 1979.; Whitney. 2003).

6. Agreement Patterns

Russian exhibits agreement patterns between nouns and their modifiers. Adjectives, pronouns, and determiners must agree with the number of the noun they modify. This agreement occurs in terms of number, case, and gender (Corbett, 2000). For example, in the phrase "интересная студентка" (interesting student, feminine), the adjective "интересная" (interesting) agrees with the noun "студентка" (student) in number, gender, and case. Since the noun "студентка" is in singular number, feminine gender, and nominative case, the adjective "интересная" also takes singular number, feminine gender, and nominative case (Corbett. 2000).

Sanskrit, similar to Russian, also displays agreement patterns between nouns and their modifiers. Adjectives, pronouns, and determiners agree with the number, case, and gender of the noun they modify (Whitney. 2003). For instance, in the sentence "वृक्षाः हरिताः सन्ति" (The trees are green), the adjective "हरिताः" (green) agrees with the plural noun "वृक्षाः" (trees) in number, case, and gender. As the noun "वृक्षाः" is in plural number, the adjective "हरिताः" also takes the plural form (Macdonell, A. A. 2014; Whitney, W. D. 1896; Joshi, S. D. 1979). Additionally, the adjective agrees with the noun in gender and case, ensuring grammatical agreement (Whitney. 2003).

The agreement patterns observed in both Russian and Sanskrit demonstrate the importance of maintaining grammatical agreement between nouns and their modifiers. In both languages,

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adjectives, pronouns, and determiners adjust their forms to match the number, case, and gender of the nouns they modify. This agreement enhances the clarity and grammatical accuracy of the language.

7. *Syntactic Structures*

Russian and Sanskrit employ specific syntactic structures to express numbers, ensuring clarity and agreement between subject and verb (Flier, Michael.1972; Isačenko, A. V., Forsyth, J., & Isacenko, A. V. 1972; Morris, S., & Forsyth, J.1971; Nicholson, J. G., Forsyth, J., & Ward, D. 1973). In Russian, the order of words in a sentence typically follows the Subject-Verb-Object pattern. The endings of the noun, when serving as the subject, and the verb convey the number, and both subject and verb agree with each other in number. For example, in the sentence "Студент читает книгу" (Student reads a book), the subject is singular, and the verb also takes the singular form (Dunn, J. A., & Khairov, S. 2013; Kemple, B. 2012; Wade, T. 2020; Bailyn 2012).

Similarly, Sanskrit follows a relatively fixed word order within a sentence, with the typical pattern being Subject-Object-Verb. In the sentence "सः पुस्तकं पठति" (He reads a book), both the subject and the verb are in the singular form, agreeing with each other in number (Macdonell, A. A. 2014; Whitney, W. D. 1896; Joshi, S. D. 1979). However, in Sanskrit, conveying number unambiguously relies not only on the syntactic structure but also on case inflections and agreement patterns. These morphological markers ensure accurate expression of numbers in the language (Whitney. 2003).

In both Russian and Sanskrit, the combination of syntactic structures and morphological markers is critical for properly conveying numbers. The word order and agreement patterns in sentences aid in the establishment of the relationship between subject and verb, ensuring that they are numerically equal. Furthermore, in both languages, inflectional endings and case markers provide additional clarity and clarification of numbers.

These syntactic and morphological traits contribute to Russian and Sanskrit grammatical systems, allowing speakers to represent numbers accurately and clearly. They represent the languages' diversity and complexity, as well as their ability to transmit numerical values within phrases.

8. *Semantic Aspects*

As a linguistic category, number includes more than just grammatical distinctions. It also has semantic implications that influence how nouns are interpreted in a language. It can be learnt about how numbers influence the meaning and interpretation of nouns by investigating the semantic distinctions, quantification methods, and conceptualizations related with numbers. The plural number has distinct semantic connections in both Russian and Sanskrit that go beyond basic quantity.

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In Russian, the plural is frequently connected with greater generality or inclusion. In Russian, plural nouns can be used to represent approximate quantities or vague meanings. When referring to a category as a whole rather than specific individual instances, the plural form allows for a more generalised reference. Furthermore, the plural in Russian can have honorific or rhetorical connotation, lending grandeur or emphasis to the statement (Corbett. 2000). Similarly, in Sanskrit, the plural number is associated with generality, inclusivity, or collectivity. Plural forms in Sanskrit can communicate a broader sense of reference, stressing a group's or category's collective nature (Whitney. 2003). The plural form provides for a more complete or all-encompassing understanding. Furthermore, plural forms in Sanskrit, like Russian, can be used for honorific purposes or to lend rhetorical emphasis to a sentence (Macdonell. 1914).

In Russian and Sanskrit, the semantic connotations of the plural number reflect the subtle ways in which numbers impact the perception of nouns. Plural forms broaden the referential span by stressing generality, inclusiveness, and collective conceptions. Furthermore, the plural can be used for honorific or rhetorical purposes, adding layers of meaning and impact to the conversation. In Russian, the distinction between singular and plural entities extends beyond mere numerical quantity. The choice of number in Russian nouns can convey various semantic nuances, providing additional layers of meaning to the discourse (Corbett. 2000). For example, the noun "дом" (house) in the plural form "дома" (houses) can imply a collective sense, referring to a group of houses or a neighborhood. The plural form emphasizes the unity and shared characteristics of the houses in that group. This collective reference adds a semantic nuance beyond the simple numerical count.

Furthermore, the plural form in Russian can convey distributivity, suggesting that the action or attribute applies to each individual element within the set. For instance, the phrase "они пели песни" (they sang songs) indicates that each individual member of the group sang their own song. The plural form "песни" highlights the distributive nature of the action, emphasizing that multiple songs were sung by different individuals within the group (Corbett. 2000). Similarly, in Sanskrit, the choice between singular and plural nouns carries semantic distinctions related to collective reference, distributivity, and genericity (Whitney. 2003). For example, the noun "पुस्तकः" (book) in the plural form "पुस्तकाः" (books) can imply a collective sense, referring to a collection of books or a library (Macdonell, A. A. 2014; Whitney, W. D. 1896; Joshi, S. D. 1979.). The plural form emphasizes the collective nature of the books, highlighting their shared characteristics or their existence as a set.

Additionally, the plural form in Sanskrit can also convey distributivity, indicating that the action or attribute applies to each individual element within the set. For instance, the phrase "अहम् पठामि पुस्तकानि" (I read books) suggests that each individual book is being read separately. The plural form "पुस्तकानि" emphasizes the distributive nature of the action, indicating that multiple books are being read individually (Whitney. 2003).

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In both Russian and Sanskrit, the semantic distinctions related with the use of singular and plural nouns give depth and richness to the articulation of concepts. These languages use numbers to convey notions such as collectively, distributivity, and genericity, expanding the meaning and interpretation of nouns in a variety of settings.

9. *Quantification and Conceptualizations*

To express numbers in Russian, different quantification strategies are used, including singular, plural, and a specific dual number category (Forsyth. 1970). When referring to entities that appear in pairs or twos, the availability of the dual number in Russian allows for precise quantification. This linguistic trait reflects the way Russian speakers perceive and categorise the world and indicates the cultural and intellectual relevance of duality in the Russian language. It highlights the significance of pairs and twofold entities in linguistic and cultural expressions (Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D. 2009). It is crucial to note, however, that not all Russian nouns are marked for the dual grammatical number, and verbs do not have a dual number category (Forsyth. 1970).

Sanskrit, too, uses quantification strategies to express numbers. Sanskrit has a dual number category in addition to singular and plural forms (Pini, 6th century BCE). The dual number is included in Sanskrit to emphasise the cultural and intellectual relevance of duality for Sanskrit speakers. It emphasises the acceptance of dual entities as well as the significance of duality in their understanding and depiction of the world.

The prevalence of the dual number in both Russian and Sanskrit languages demonstrate the respective societies' cultural and cognitive relevance of duality. It demonstrates how these languages can be used to express and quantify pairs or double items. Russian and Sanskrit speakers display their distinct conceptualization and categorization of the world by including the dual number (Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D. 2009).

10. *Cultural Perspectives*

The semantics of numbers in Russian and Sanskrit provide useful insights into the cultural perspectives ingrained in both languages. The specific semantic distinctions, quantification strategies, and conceptualizations linked with numbers reflect the speakers' cultural values, societal conventions, and conceptual frameworks. By investigating these cultural viewpoints, we can acquire a better understanding of the cultural and linguistic worldviews of Russian and Sanskrit speakers (Cuzzolin, P. 2006; Fortson, B. 2006; Joseph, B.D. 2009).

The semantic elements of numbers in Russian convey cultural viewpoints on collectively, inclusiveness, and accuracy in quantification. For example, the inclusion of a particular dual number category in Russian demonstrates the importance of duality in Russian speakers' view of the world (Forsyth. 1970). This implies a cultural emphasis on pairs or double entities, emphasising the recognition and significance of duality in various realms of life.

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Additionally, the choice of number in Russian nouns can express extra meaning nuances beyond plain numerical quantity. In Russian, for example, the plural form might be connected with generality, inclusion, or approximation (Corbett, 2000). These semantic contrasts give insight on how Russian speakers view and categorise the world, highlighting cultural values like as collective reference, distributivity, and larger conceptualizations of entities. Similarly, the semantic elements of numbers in Sanskrit indicate cultural ideas on collectively, duality, and accuracy in quantification. The introduction of a separate dual number category in Sanskrit demonstrates the cultural relevance of duality in Sanskrit speakers' view of the world (Pini, 6th century BCE). This shows a cultural appreciation of the relevance of dual beings and duality in various aspects of life.

Furthermore, in Sanskrit, the distinction between single and plural nouns carries meaning distinctions related to collective reference, distributivity, and genericity (Whitney, 2003). These semantic variations reveal how Sanskrit speakers perceive and interpret the world, reflecting cultural ideals such as inclusion, communal identity, and larger entity conceptualizations.

By investigating the semantic elements of numbers in Russian and Sanskrit, it finds cultural perspectives and obtain a deeper knowledge of the cultural and linguistic worldviews of these languages' speakers. These findings add to our understanding of the cultural values, societal norms, and conceptual frameworks that shape the language systems and cultural activities of Russian and Sanskrit-speaking populations (Cuzzolin, P., 2006; Fortson, B., 2006; Joseph, B.D. (2009).

11. Language Typology Implications

The comparison of Russian and Sanskrit grammatical number systems provides useful insights into language typology and cross-linguistic patterns. It is found that universal tendencies and unique aspects that impact the expression of numbers across different linguistic systems by exploring the similarities and contrasts between these two languages. For expressing numbers, both Russian and Sanskrit have sophisticated inflectional systems with specific morphological markers. Both languages use inflectional endings on nouns, adjectives, and pronouns to identify singular and plural forms (Corbett, 2000). The occurrence of such inflectional marking draws attention to a shared element of their grammatical number systems.

Sanskrit, on the other hand, introduces new characteristics that contribute to its distinct morphological system for expressing numbers. The inclusion of the dual number category, which allows for the precise quantification of pairs or double items (Pini, 6th century BCE), is one important characteristic. This separates Sanskrit from Russian, as Russian does not have a productive dual number system (Forsyth, 1970). The "pada" agreement system, which incorporates special agreement markers for case in verb conjugation, is another distinguishing feature of Sanskrit. This agreement system ensures that numbers are expressed correctly by

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using verb forms that agree with the number and case of the subject and object (Macdonell, 1914).

The study of the syntactic characteristics of grammatical numbers in Russian and Sanskrit provides intriguing implications for language typology. To convey numbers, both languages use agreement patterns and syntactic structures. Russian, on the other hand, allows for more flexibility in word order within phrases and sentences, providing for distinct differentiation between singular and plural forms (Bailyn, 2012). This adaptability adds to a more adaptable and changeable word order, which is shared by many Indo-European languages. Sanskrit, on the other hand, relies on tight word order and strong morphological indicators to accurately express numerals. The sequence of words inside a phrase, such as the Subject-Object-Verb order, is critical for conveying the intended meaning and avoiding ambiguity (Whitney, 2003).

These findings show the various strategies used among languages to express numbers and help us comprehend language typology. A comparison of the morphological and syntactic elements of grammatical numbers in Russian and Sanskrit provides useful insights into cross-linguistic patterns, universal tendencies, and language-specific traits.

12. Conclusion

This article provides a thorough comparison of the number systems in Russian and Sanskrit. The study looks at morphological, syntactic, and semantic characteristics, discovering both similarities and differences. The research also included a comparison of the morphological characteristics of Numbers in Russian and Sanskrit. It investigated their inflectional processes, morphological markers, and distinguishing characteristics, demonstrating the varied strategies used for each language. It also examined noun phrases, agreement patterns, and syntactic structures linked to expressing Numbers in both languages. The study provided insight on the semantic complexities and cultural viewpoints encoded in these languages by studying semantic distinctions, quantification strategies, and conceptualizations related to Numbers.

The study adds to our understanding of cross-linguistic variation and closeness, semantic implications of Numbers, and cultural factors influencing language expression and language typology by revealing how languages from different families use different ways to express Number. The findings help us comprehend the various morphological structures utilised to express numbers and give light on the typological variance between languages.

The findings also report Russian and Sanskrit's distinct grammatical traits and patterns. More research in this area will elucidate and illuminate the fundamental concepts behind the representation of Grammatical Number. Research in this field will improve our understanding of language diversity, proximity, and language typology, as well as deepen our understanding of the intricate morphological systems found in various languages.

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